

Ruralities

**RURALITIES - CLIMATE SMART, ECOSYSTEM-ENHANCING AND
KNOWLEDGE-BASED RURAL EXPERTISE AND TRAINING CENTRES**

D1.4 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN – UPDATED

VERSION

Deliverable D1.4

WP1 – Management

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Abstract

The project 'Climate smart, ecosystem-enhancing and knowledge-based rural expertise and training centres' (RURALITIES) delivers an ecosystem-enhancing and climate action driven expertise and learning framework organised in hubs e.g., the 'RURALITIES', comprising a series of innovative methodologies with the learner at its core, supported by a comprehensive network of living labs, and a blockchain-based digital platform combining the Internet and wireless technologies, to assist engage, connect and empower actors. This is done via a multi-point approach, e.g., multi-actors, multi-disciplines, multi-systems, multi-scale, multi-sectors, and multilevel.

RURALITIES is rooted in the recruitment, preparation, training, and coaching of 1,000+ facilitators for a variety of tasks (e.g., trainers, facilitators, role models, hub coordinators, etc.), and who play a significant role in creating the matrix and the platform upon which the learning framework is built, develops, and evolves. RURALITIES proposes to ideate, implement, futureproof, validate, and deliver the expertise and learning centres via real-scale practicing in 6 simplified rural socio-ecological systems (SIMSES) e.g., demonstrators, 2 in Italy, 1 in the United- Kingdom (UK), 1 in Slovenia, 1 in Spain and 1 in Romania. RURALITIES coordinates identified actions of local, regional authorities in supports of rural innovation in regions and economic sectors where rural innovators are not yet engaged in a relevant network.

RURALITIES coordinates identified SIMSES networks promoting rural innovation solutions whilst establishing innovative multipoint 'RURALITIES Hubs' of expertise and training on rural innovation. This is done via coordinating action for the managing authorities and regional bodies influencing regional and national policy instruments in Italy, the UK, Slovenia, Spain and in Romania.

Partners

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	COO	PEDAL	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	SK
2	BEN	RDRP	ASOCIATIA RURAL DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH PLATFORM	RO
4	BEN	ASIN	ASOCIACION DE INVESTIGACION DE INDUSTRIAS CARNICAS DEL PRINCIPADO DE ASTURIAS	ES
5	BEN	NIC	KEMIJSKI INSTITUT	SI
6	BEN	UPM	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
7	BEN	IRI	INSTITUT ZA RAZVOJ I INOVACIJE - IRI	RS
8	BEN	PART	PARTICULA GROUP DRUSTVO S OGRANICENOM ODGOVORNOSCU ZA ISTRAZIVANJE RAZVOJ I PROIZVODNJU	HR
9	BEN	UNIZG	SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU AGRONOMSKI FAKULTET	HR
10	BEN	ACTS	AFRICAN CENTRE FOR TECHNOLOGY STUDIES	KE
11	BEN	CITT	CENTRO DE INVESTIGACAO E TRANSFERENCIA DE TECNOLOGIA PARA DESENVOLVIMENTO COMUNITARIO	MZ
12	BEN	EQUIP	EUROPEAN SOCIETY FOR QUALITY AND PATIENT SAFETY IN GENERAL PRACTICE/ FAMILY MEDICINE	DK
13	BEN	MUNI	MUGLA SITKI KOÇMAN UNIVERSITY	TR
14	BEN	MARIN	MARIN BIYOTEKNOLOJİ URUNLERİ VE GIDA SANAYİ TİCARET LIMITED ŞİRKETİ	TR
15	BEN	ULB	UNIVERSITE LIBRE DE BRUXELLES	BE
16	BEN	INAG	INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EXTERN VERZELFSTANDIGD AGENTSCHAP IN PRIVAATRECHTELIJKE VORM VZW	BE
17	BEN	AASTMT	ARAB ACADEMY FOR SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND MARITIME TRANSPORT	EG
18	BEN	RRAP	REGIONALNA RAZVOJNA AGENCIJA POSAVJE	SI
19	BEN	YXSAV	YXS AVALANA SRL	RO
20	BEN	UNIVI	UNIVERSITATEA PENTRU STIINTELE VIETII "ION IONESCU DE LA BRAD" DIN IASI	RO
21	BEN	SIRET	ASOCIATIA GRUPUL DE ACTIUNE LOCALA SIRET-MOLDOVA	RO
22	BEN	SUA	Sokoine University of Agriculture	TZ
23	BEN	UNINO	UNIVERSITE DE NOUAKCHOTT AL AASRIYA	MR

24	BEN	IFAYA	INSTITUT FACULTAIRE DES SCIENCESAGRONOMIQUES (IFA) DE YANGAMBI	CD
25	BEN	ACD	ALTERNATIVE COMMUNAUTAIRE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE (ACDD)	CI
27	BEN	AMVO	ALMANAR VOLUNTARY ORGANIZATION	SD
28	BEN	CDD	COMMUNICATION POUR UN DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE C.D.D.	TG
29	BEN	YTED	YOUTHS IN TECHNOLOGY AND DEVELOPMENT UGANDA LIMITED	UG
30	BEN	CTIC	FUNDACION CTIC CENTRO TECNOLOGICO PARA EL DESARROLLO EN ASTURIAS DE LAS TECNOLOGIAS DE LA INFORMACION	ES
31	BEN	FHV	FONDAZIONE HOMO VIATOR - SAN TEBALDO	IT
32	BEN	MOFE	MONTEFELTRO SVILUPPO SCARL	IT
33	BEN	MUSE	MUSEUM GRAPHIA	IT
34	BEN	CDM	LA CORTE DELLA MINIERA SRL	IT
35	BEN	DEX	DESARROLLO DE ESTRATEGIAS EXTERIORES SA	ES
36	BEN	REDA	ASOCIACION RED ASTURIANA DE DESARROLLO RURAL	ES
37	BEN	GMV	MONTAGNA VICENTINA SOCIETA COOPERATIVA	IT
38	BEN	MARA	MAROC HORIZON D'AVENTURES	MA
39	BEN	UNWI	UNIVERSITY OF MALAWI	MW
40	BEN	NOMA	OKMNOMADS.ORG	GH
41	BEN	UNIM	MAGYAR AGRAR- ES ELETTUDOMANYI EGYETEM	HU
43	BEN	UASZ	UNIVERSITE ASSANE SECK DE ZIGUINCHOR	SN
44	BEN	CPF	CONFEDERATION PAYSANNE DU FASO	BF
45	BEN	UNAD	UNIVERSITY OF RWANDA	RW
46	BEN	ZLAN	ZAMBIA LAND ALLIANCE	ZM
47	BEN	EVRO	EVROSAD PROIZVODNJA TRGOVINA EVETOVANJE D.O.O. KRSKO	SI
48	BEN	SEVO	TURISTICNO DRUSTVO SENOVO	SI
49	BEN	IISAC	ISTITUTO D'ISTRUZIONE SUPERIORE A CECCHI	IT
50	AP	HITP	THE HIGHLANDS AND ISLANDS TRANSPORT PARTNERSHIP	UK
52	AP	EW	CONSERVATION EDUCATION AND RESEARCH TRUST	UK
53	BEN	APO	APODISSI LTD	NG

Abbreviations

Acronym	Description
AP	Associated Partner
AU	African Union
BEN	Beneficiary
COO	Coordinator
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
G-Drive	Google Drive
ICD	Informed Consent Document
ICF	Informed Consent Form
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
RURALITIES	Climate smart, ecosystem-enhancing and knowledge-based rural expertise and training centres
RURNEX	RURALITIES Nexus
SIMSES	Simplified rural socio-ecological systems
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Executive summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) main goal is to cover the data management processes of RURALITIES, ensuring an alignment with Horizon Europe FAIR data principles (data must be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). The DMP is a living document which is being released three times along the project, updated with the periodic evaluation and assessment and adding levels of detail and granularity as processes for data collection progress.

D1.4 is the second version of the DMP and describes updates in current data management practices and frameworks, establishes links with Ethics and Data Protection regulations, and shows how the different data management policies have been effectively handled within the project. This second version of the DMP provides some updated highlights to be useful to other research projects related to rural development and innovation, as well as to interested stakeholders.

1.2 Deliverable structure

This deliverable is structured following the guidelines of the Horizon programme on FAIR Data Management including the following information:

- **Section 2.** Describes the changes in the data collection and management strategies, compared to the first version of the “Data Management Plan” (Deliverable D1.2)
- **Section 3.** Introduces the updated legal and ethical frameworks, with a special focus on illiterate people and stakeholders.
- **Section 4.** Explains how the different data management policies have been effectively handled within the project.
- **Section 5.** Conclusions

2. CHANGES IN DATA COLLECTION AND MANAGEMENT

In this section we are describing the new processes to be considered in RURALITIES project regarding data collection and management. Section 2.1 describes the new Zenodo repository for the project, while Section 2.2 discusses the 2ES monitoring tools for experimental data management in WP2.

2.1 Zenodo repository

In order to collect in a unique repository all experimental data produced in the context of RURALITIES project, a Zenodo repository was established. Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, datasets, research software, reports, and any other research-related digital artifacts.

In this repository, all partners can upload the original experimental data. Each dataset includes the applicable license. Curation methodology is publicly described as well.

Currently, seven different datasets can be accessed in the Zenodo repository. The table below describes every single artifact, including the data management license.

Table 1 – RURALITIES Datasets published in the Zenodo repository

Dataset title	Description	Responsible partner	License
The Evolution of the Romanian Organic Agriculture in a Global Context	Organic agriculture is widely considered an agricultural method that aims to produce food products by turning to natural processes and substances, limiting, at the same time, the impact on the environment.	Academia Română, Filiala Iași	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Drought-Induced Yield Decline in Maize (Zea mays) and Sunflower (Helianthus annuus) Crops: a Case Study of Agricultural Vulnerability in Iași County, Romania	The rising trend of global temperatures and significant alterations in precipitation patterns present formidable challenges for Romania, which is currently experiencing extended periods of drought. The prevailing conditions have profoundly impacted agricultural production, leading to significant economic and social consequences.	Academia Română, Filiala Iași	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
RURALITIES_1st Newsletter		Centre for Technology Research & Innovation (Cyprus)	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Long-Term Experiences with Fertilizers on Wheat		Academia Română, Filiala Iași	Creative Commons Attribution

and Maize Crops in the Pedoclimatic Conditions of the Bârlad Plateau			4.0 International
Capitolul 1. LUMILE RURALE ALE MARILOR ORAȘE		Academia Română, Filiala Iași	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Sisteme rurale durabile și sustenabile Studii de agro-economie și antropologie rurală		Academia Română, Filiala Iași	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
The Evolution of the Romanian Organic Agriculture in a Global Context	The aim of this work is to analyse the evolution of the Romanian organic agriculture over a period of 12 years, between 2010-2021, especially regarding the organic cultivated area and crop's structure, having also in view the global context of the agricultural organic sector. The analysis highlighted an important development of the organic area during this timeframe, based, mainly, on permanent grassland, cereals, industrial crops and "other crops", at the end of the interval Romania being among the countries with the highest contribution to the increase of the European organic land area	Academia Română, Filiala Iași	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

As can be seen "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International" is the commonly used. Under this license any stakeholder is free to:

- Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format for any purpose, even commercially.
- Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.
- But the licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms.

Under the following terms:

- Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.
- No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

2.2 2ES monitoring tool

In the context of WP2, and in the period covered by this deliverable D1.4 (from April 2023 to September 2025) a new data collection process has started regarding activity monitoring and impact assessment. A system to collect evidence about experiments, as well as a monitoring tool to extract statistics is provided, called the 2ES monitoring framework. This framework was planned within the scope of the WP2 impact case, as was mainly developed within the framework of Task 2.4. The impact case defined a timeline for implementing the 2ES monitoring framework, as follows:

- 11th March 2024: Decision on the format of the data collection activity, based on the results of the Technology preference survey (see D2.4 Section 4.2).
- 12th December 2024: Creation of first template and sharing the template with SIMSES participants to collect feedback on the template structure and requested data.
- 10th January 2025: Deadline for collecting feedback
- 19 January: Release of the 2ES monitoring framework. The spreadsheet is open for edition by SIMSES participants. Asking for contributions.
- End of April 2025: First impact overview. Analysing partner’s input.
- End of July 2024: Second impact overview. Analysing partner’s input.

Table 2 – RURALITIES 2ES Monitoring framework description to partners

RURALITIES 2ES Monitoring framework		
The RURALITIES 2ES Monitoring framework is a multilayer index system to assist visualizing / evaluating experiment progress throughout the project		
This index ensures impact assessment of the project’s experiments (pilots/demonstrators) and also ensures measuring, thus keeping the balance between the 2ES pillars, whilst activating potential opportunities for cross-linking.		
RURALITIES 2ES Monitoring framework usage		
Data will be collected and included in this monitoring framework for SIMSES consultation and adaptation.		
Data collection: Starting in January 2025. The target of these surveys will be all partners that generate experiments (experiment owners), they may be SIMSES or not. However, monitoring and presentation of results are structured around SIMSES, as this entity can provide objectives and individual assessment plans.		
Data validation: The impact will be calculated quarterly. This is the initial calendar for impact evaluation:		
April 2025	Impact assessment overview - First quarter	It will be reported in D2.4 Technical report on the implementation of the project’s impact monitoring and assessment (M36)
July 2025	Impact assessment overview - Second quarter	
October 2025	Impact assessment overview - Third quarter	
January 2026	Impact assessment overview - Fourth quarter	It will be reported in D2.5 Technical reports on the implementation of the project’s impact monitoring and assessment, version 2 (M48)
April 2026	Impact assessment overview - Fifth quarter	
July 2026	Impact assessment overview - Sixth quarter	
October 2026	Impact assessment overview - Seventh quarter	It will be reported in D2.6 Technical reports on the implementation of the project’s impact monitoring and assessment, final version (M60)
January 2027	Impact assessment overview - Eighth quarter	
April 2027	Impact assessment overview - Ninth quarter	
July 2027	Impact assessment overview - Tenth quarter	

As part of this data collection process, partners are required to enter any event/experiment/workshop that contributed to impact in RURALITIES and provide information related to Economic / Societal and Environmental impact, along with materials and evidence. The structure of the activity log is as follows:

1. General Part: Activity name, short description, Responsible partners (Participating partners)¹, Type of activity, Type of result, Activity date (MM/DD/YYYY), Number of online attendants, Number of in-person attendants.
2. Economic Impact: Number of involved employees/entrepreneurs, Number of (tentative) angel investors² / funding bodies, Number of companies/startups engaged, Potential target for investment, others.
3. Societal impact: Number of young people (< 30) Number of immigrants, Number of women, Number of other vulnerable groups (minorities, elderly, minorities, refugees, etc.), Number of rural experts, Number of social partners, authorities, etc., other goals.
4. Environmental impact (Supported by evaluation rubric included in Annex 2):
 - To what degree this activity is related to sustainable farming and agri-food?
 - To what degree is related to the creation/improvement of policies
 - To what degree is related to the preservation of natural spaces?
 - To what degree is related to enhancing circularity?
 - To what degree is related to reducing carbon emissions?
 - Other
5. Material - Evidence: Links to images, video, files etc. that give background information of the result.

As a result of this data collection process, and as of the date of preparation of this deliverable, a total of 133 activities were collected. Eighty-five of these activities have incorporated additional multimedia material in the form of links to resource descriptions, photographs, presentation documents, or social media posts. Additional information on this data collection process and the results of the methodology proposed by the 2ES framework can be found in the D2.4³.

2.3 Cybersecurity Measures

Cybersecurity compliance

In response to the Ethics Check recommendations, RURALITIES has explicitly aligned its digital platforms and data management practices with the NIS2 Directive. Strengthened safeguards include the use of secure cloud environments with restricted access, multi-factor authentication where possible, and scheduled security audits. These measures reinforce protection against potential breaches and ensure the privacy and security of all participants. Table 3 shows the cybersecurity measures to be applied.

Personal data processing

¹ RURALITIES Beneficiary/Beneficiaries that carried out the activity (in parentheses, other RURALITIES beneficiaries that participated in the activity)

² An angel investor (also known as a business angel, informal investor, angel funder, private investor, or seed investor) is an individual who provides capital to a business or businesses, including startups, usually in exchange for convertible debt or ownership equity.

³ No link is provided to this deliverable, as it is of a Sensitive nature, and therefore, limited under the conditions of the RURALITIES' Grant Agreement.

RURALITIES processes only a limited set of personal data categories, namely basic contact details, demographic information, professional profiles, and participants' opinions. All processing activities are carried out in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and applicable national legislation.

Response to Ethics Check (July 2025)

Following the Ethics Check Report, which highlighted the need to reinforce cybersecurity provisions, the consortium has introduced enhanced protocols, including:

- Secure cloud environments with restricted access
- Multi-factor authentication mechanisms, where possible
- Regularly scheduled security audits
- Clear notification protocols ensuring that, in the event of a data breach, relevant authorities and affected individuals are informed within 72 hours

Privacy by design and by default

All data collection tools (e.g., mobile applications, online surveys) are configured to minimise privacy risks from the outset. Wherever feasible, anonymisation or pseudonymisation techniques are applied to further protect participant identities, ensuring that data is managed responsibly and ethically throughout its lifecycle.

Measure	Description	Responsible Partner(s)
Secure cloud environments	Restricted-access cloud platforms with role-based permissions.	IT Partner / Coordinator
Multi-factor authentication (MFA)	MFA for access to project platforms and sensitive datasets.	IT Partner / All Partners
Scheduled security audits	Regular third-party audits to test the resilience of systems and detect vulnerabilities.	IT Partner / Coordinator
Data breach notification protocol	Authorities and affected individuals are informed within 72 hours of any breach.	Coordinator / Ethics Manager
Privacy by design and by default	Default minimisation of data collection, configured privacy settings.	All Partners / Ethics Manager
Compliance with GDPR and NIS2 Directive	Continuous monitoring of legal compliance and adaptation of practices.	Coordinator / Ethics Manager

Table 3 – Cybersecurity measures

3. UPDATED ETHICS AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

RURALITIES project is a living environment, as well as the social and technical ecosystems. In this section we discuss the data management plan for two emerging new situations within the project: the legal implications of the multi-actor repository regarding data collection (Section 3.1); and the different strategies we followed to ensure informed consent when illiterate people participate in the project's activities (Section 3.2).

3.1 Data management and GDPR in Multi-actor repository

The multi-actor repository is an online platform repository of 10.000+ (KPI) actors of the RURNex (worldwide). The dissemination level is PU-Public. The platform is envisioned to have the most diverse stakeholder groups possible: from individual rural actors (e.g., active citizens) to companies and EU projects.

According to the original data management plan, the project agreed to collect only publicly available data, and we don't obtain data directly from stakeholders.

Nonetheless, the GDPR states that even in that case, RURALITIES partners must act proactively towards the stakeholders whose data we are collecting and analysing. To clarify this point, we quote below GDPR art. 14, especially (*in italics*) the third sub article (information to be provided where personal data have not been obtained from the data subject)⁴:

Art. 14 GDPR: Information to be provided where personal data have not been obtained from the data subject

Where personal data have not been obtained from the data subject, the controller shall provide the data subject with the following information:

1. the identity and the contact details of the controller and, where applicable, of the controller's representative;
2. the contact details of the data protection officer, where applicable;
3. the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis for the processing;
4. the categories of personal data concerned;
5. the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data, if any;
6. where applicable, that the controller intends to transfer personal data to a recipient in a third country or international organisation and the existence or absence of an adequacy decision by the Commission, or in the case of transfers referred to in [Article 46](#) or [47](#), or the second subparagraph of [Article 49](#)(1), reference to the appropriate or suitable safeguards and the means to obtain a copy of them or where they have been made available.

⁴ [https://gdpr-info.eu/art-14-gdpr/#:~:text=Art.,General%20Data%20Protection%20Regulation%20\(GDPR\)](https://gdpr-info.eu/art-14-gdpr/#:~:text=Art.,General%20Data%20Protection%20Regulation%20(GDPR))

In addition to the information referred to in paragraph 1, the controller shall provide the data subject with the following information necessary to ensure fair and transparent processing in respect of the data subject:

1. the period for which the personal data will be stored, or if that is not possible, the criteria used to determine that period;
2. where the processing is based on point (f) of [Article 6\(1\)](#), the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party;
3. the existence of the right to request from the controller access to and rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing concerning the data subject and to object to processing as well as the right to data portability;
4. where processing is based on point (a) of [Article 6\(1\)](#) or point (a) of [Article 9\(2\)](#), the existence of the right to withdraw consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
5. the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority;
6. from which source the personal data originate, and if applicable, whether it came from publicly accessible sources;
7. the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in [Article 22\(1\)](#) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.

The controller shall provide the information referred to in paragraphs 1 and 2:

1. within a reasonable period after obtaining the personal data, but at the latest within one month, having regard to the specific circumstances in which the personal data are processed;
2. if the personal data are to be used for communication with the data subject, at the latest at the time of the first communication to that data subject; or
3. if a disclosure to another recipient is envisaged, at the latest when the personal data are first disclosed.

Where the controller intends to further process the personal data for a purpose other than that for which the personal data were obtained, the controller shall provide the data subject prior to that further processing with information on that other purpose and with any relevant further information as referred to in paragraph 2.

Paragraphs 1 to 4 shall not apply where and insofar as:

1. the data subject already has the information;
2. the provision of such information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort, in particular for processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in [Article 89\(1\)](#) or in so far as the obligation referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the objectives of that processing. In such cases the controller shall take appropriate measures to protect the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, including making the information publicly available;
3. obtaining or disclosure is expressly laid down by Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject and which provides appropriate measures to protect the data subject's legitimate interests; or

4. where the personal data must remain confidential subject to an obligation of professional secrecy regulated by Union or Member State law, including a statutory obligation of secrecy.

Then, current discussions with legal experts and partners seem to indicate that RURALITIES project might be exempt from this due to the sheer number of stakeholders we are mapping.

For additional clarity, below is quoted the GDPR art. 89 (Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes)⁵:

Art. 89 GDPR: Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes

1. Processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. ²Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. ³Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. ⁴Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.
2. Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in [Articles 15, 16, 18](#) and [21](#) subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.
3. Where personal data are processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in [Articles 15, 16, 18, 19, 20](#) and [21](#) subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.
4. Where processing referred to in paragraphs 2 and 3 serves at the same time another purpose, the derogations shall apply only to processing for the purposes referred to in those paragraphs.

In conclusion, and until any contradictory argument could emerge, RURALITIES project assumes the deployment of the Multi-actor repository can continue without contacting all the participating stakeholders based on the exceptions described in GDPR.

⁵ <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-89-gdpr/>

3.2 Informed consent for illiterate people

Informed consent is an essential component of a research project⁶. Obtaining informed consent enables research and clinical procedures to be conducted both ethically and legally.

Consent is considered “informed” when given by a person who understands the purpose and the nature of research, and what is required of themselves as participants, in addition to the potential benefits and risks resulting from the study. Elements of valid consent include the capacity of participants to provide consent, disclosure of necessary and important information, freedom to choose to participate without coercion (i.e., freedom not to participate), and consent of participants.

Literacy and language are important factors for comprehension; previous studies have shown that both are educational barriers which may lead to poor comprehension or the lack of understanding consent information.

According to data from UNESCO’s Institute for Statistics in 2012, there are nearly 793 million illiterate adults in the world (age 15 and over) that represent 18% of the adult population.

It would be pointless to obtain written consent from those who are illiterate as they are unable to read an informed consent form and understand the risks and benefits. In these situations, a translator familiar with terminology is essential. Comprehension of informed consent is enhanced when researchers provide the study community or individuals with information prior to obtaining consent and when study communities are engaged in discussions about the research.

When RURALITIES partners are enrolling subjects who cannot read the consent materials provided in Deliverable 1.2, due to illiteracy, it is recommended to proceed as described below:

- It is recommended that an impartial witness observe the consent process.
- Consent materials should be presented orally.
- Sufficient time should be allowed for questions to be asked and answered, both by the subject, and by the person obtaining consent to ensure the subject comprehends the consent information.
- Consider using a video/audio recording of the consent discussion as part of the documentation of informed consent.

The consent form should document the method used for communication with the prospective subject and the specific means by which the prospective subject communicated agreement to participate in the study.

To document the consent process, the RURALITIES recommendations are consistent with guidance endorsed by the International Conference on Harmonisation (although described for the medical research, it is applicable to many other scenarios such as RURALITIES actions). If, as commonly required from illiterate people, the subject verbally agrees to participate in the study, RURALITIES partners are recommended to proceed as follows:

- If capable of doing so, the subject signs, or marks an X to signify consent.

⁶ Alaei M, Pourshams A, Altaha N, Goglan G, Jafari E. Obtaining informed consent in an illiterate population. Middle East J Dig Dis. 2013 Jan;5(1):37-40. PMID: 24829668; PMCID: PMC3990137.

- The witness signs and personally dates the consent form. By doing so, the witness attests that the consent information was accurately explained and that the subject apparently understood the information, and informed consent was given freely.
- The person obtaining consent signs and dates the consent form.
- Signed copies are given to the subject.

To facilitate the obtention of the informed consent from illiterate people, partners are provided with the diagram below, described by Chatterjee et al.⁷. Where ICF indicates “Informed Consent Form” and ICD refers the “Informed Consent Document” (which includes the document method). Figure 1 (left) is applicable when literate witnesses are available, while Figure 1 (right) is applicable when all witnesses are illiterate as well.

Figure 1 (left) – Process of obtaining written informed consent in case of an illiterate participant, (right) – Process of obtaining written informed consent in case of an illiterate participant with illiterate legally acceptable representative

Since this process constitutes an integral component of the project’s ethical framework, it is also covered in the updated version of **D3.3 – Report on the Framework for Human Participation, Animal Ethics, Environment, Health, and Safety (M36)**. The Ethics Manager (UNIZG), in close collaboration with the coordinator (PEDAL), is responsible for overseeing and ensuring compliance with these procedures.

⁷ Chatterjee, K., & Das, N. K. (2021). Informed consent in biomedical research: Scopes and challenges. Indian Dermatology Online Journal, 12(4), 529-535.

4. OVERVIEW ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DATA MANAGEMENT POLICIES

RURALITIES project monitors the catalogue of activities developed by partners with stakeholders, general public and society every six months. Implications of GDPR and data management are considered as well.

In general, activities are dissemination actions which do not require any personal or private data to be collected. So, no data management policies must be implemented. However, in some few cases (four activities, to be precise -in red background-), some critical information is handled. Table below (Table 3) includes a description with details about all these activities.

As can be seen, in all cases the name and email are collected. In general, just for future communication purposes. But, in one case, the municipality of residence was also collected to identify how many local people are attending the project's activities. In most cases, besides, the purpose of these collected data is internal (project related).

For all activities, partners are totally informed about data management strategies within the project. Even for those actions where no data is originally related, a responsible partner is indicated (see table below). If any conflict emerges regarding data policies, responsible partners must inform UPM (P6) as soon as possible to evaluate new circumstances and special cases.

		Basic Info			Activity details		Audience of the activity		Personal Data Handling		
Partner (ID)	Other partners involved	Date of activity (DD/MM/YYYY)	Place of activity	Contributors	Type of activity	Title of event	Type	Overall No of participants	Has this activity collected personal data?	Purpose of collection this personal data	Responsible Partner(s)
OCTOBER 2022 – MARCH 2023											
UNIZG (P9)	NO	3/11/2022	Online	Marko vinceković	Participation in other type of event	"agritech and foodtech" at mindspace university	Scientific community				UNIZG (P9)
RDRP (P2)	NO	18/11/2022	Online	Ioan sebastian brumă, codrin dinu vasiliu, sonia bulei, lucian tanasă	Participation in a conference	Rural development through knowledge transfer/ dezvoltare rurală prin transfer de cunoaștere (saar national symposium)	General public				RDRP (P2)
CTIC (P30)	NO	12/12/2022	Online	Covadonga cima	Press release	Press release	General public				CTIC (P30)
CTIC (P30)	NO	12/12/2022	Online	Covadonga cima	Press release	Press release, detailed description of the project	General public				CTIC (P30)
ASINCAR (P4)	CTIC (P30), DEX (P35), REDA (P36)	22/12/2022	Online	Roberto morán	Press release	Press release	General public	Ca. 10m digital readers/month, 6th newspaper in Spain			ASINCAR (P4)
RDRP (P2)	NO	18/12/2022	Online	Sebastian bruma, codrin dinu vasiliu, lucian tanasa, sonia bulei	Participation in a conference	Agro-economics and rural anthropology symposium, communication/presentation: rural development through knowledge transfer. Launch of the RURALITIES project, financed by horizon europe	Scientific community	36			RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)	YXSAV (P19), UNIVI (P20), SIRET (P21)	11/2022	Online	Sebastian bruma	Press release	Newsletter rndr, edition no. 75 - 10/2022, a new innovative pilot rural center in Romania - RURALITIES project	General public				RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	NO	17/02/2023	Physical	Gabor mester	Participation in a conference	Startup hub educational conference	General public	20			PCS (P1)
FHV (P31)	NO	19/12/2022	Online	Viola gaudiano	Social media	Project presentation on facebook page of romea strata way	General public	Impression 568			FHV (P31)

FHV (P31)	NO	22/12/2022	Online	Viola gaudiano	Social media	Project presentation on instagram profile of romea strata way	General public	Impression 188			FHV (P31)
FHV (P31)	NO	10/2022	Online	Viola gaudiano	Website	Project presentation on romea strata way website	General public				FHV (P31)
NIC (P5)	NO	9.-12/1/2023	Koper, slovenia	Beti vidmar	Other	Kick-off meeting for horizon project "remedies"	Scientific community	70			NIC (P5)
GMV (P37)	NO	23/01/2023	Online	Anna baldo	Social media	Project presentation on facebook page of gal montagna vicentina	General public	Impressions 59			GMV (P37)
PCS (P1)	NO	08/02/2023	Online	Bruno sales da silva	Social media	Social media post	General public	384 impressions			PCS (P1)
GMV (P37)	NO	09/02/2023	Online	Michela ceola	Website	Project presentation on website of gal montagna vicentina	General public				GMV (P37)
IRI (P7)	NO	21/10/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Website	News about the project launch	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	04/11/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Website	Project description and presentation	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	05/11/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	24/10/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	04/11/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	04/11/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	24/10/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	04/11/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	24/10/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	04/11/2022	Online	Siniša borota and marina anđelković	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
UNIVI (P20)	NO	26/10/2022	Online	Coca oama	Press release	News about the project launch	General public	N/a			UNIVI (P20)
ASINCAR (P4)	CTIC (P30), DEX (P35), REDA (P36)	6/12/2022	Online	Roberto morán	Press release	Press release	General public	Ca. 10m digital readers/month, 6th newspaper in spain			ASINCAR (P4)
ASINCAR (P4)	CTIC (P30), DEX	07/12/2022	Online	Roberto morán	Press release	Press release	General public	Ca. 2,42m digital readers/month			ASINCAR (P4)

	(P35), REDA (P36)										
ASINCAR (P4)	CTIC (P30), DEX (P35), REDA (P36)	26/11/2022	Online	Roberto morán	Press release	Press release	General public				ASINCAR (P4)
ASINCAR (P4)		29/12/2022	Online	Roberto morán	Press release	Press release	General public	Ca. 10m digital readers/month, 6th newspaper in spain			ASINCAR (P4)
ASINCAR (P4)			Online	Roberto morán	Social media	Social media post	General public				ASINCAR (P4)
IRI (P7)	NO	7/3/2023	Online	Marina anđelković and siniša borota	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	7/3/2023	Online	Marina anđelković and siniša borota	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	7/3/2023	Online	Marina anđelković and siniša borota	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	7/3/2023	Online	Marina anđelković and siniša borota	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)	NO	7/3/2023	Online	Marina anđelković and siniša borota	Social media	Social media post	General public				IRI (P7)
RRAP (P18)	NIC (P5)	7.2.2023	Online	Rrap	Social media	Social media post	General public				RRAP (P18)
RRAP (P18)	NO	20.10.2022	Online	Rrap	Social media	Social media post	General public				RRAP (P18)
RRAP (P18)	NO	23.1.2023	Online	Rrap	Social media	Social media post	General public				RRAP (P18)
UPM (P6)		01/03/2023	Madrid	Ramón alcarria / borja bordel	Website	RURALITIES description in upm's website	General public	Europe			UPM (P6)
PCS (P6)		01/11/2022	Online	Gabor mester	Press release	RURALITIES – climate, ecosystem and knowledge-based expertisey	General public				PCS (P6)
FHV (P31)		13/03/2023	Aquileia - italy	Viola gaudiano	Participation in other type of event	European association of romea strata way annual assembly	Regional/local authorities	Estonia, lithuania, latvia, poland, cezch republic, austria, italy			FHV (P31)
PCS (P1)	NO	21/03/2023	Online	Bruno sales da silva	Social media	Social media post	General public	860			PCS (P1)
HIT (P50)		27/03/2023	Inverness, scotland	Jayne golding	Participation in other type of event	Visit to highland by delegation from Asturian region of Spain	Regional/local authorities	Tbc			HIT (P50)

GMV (P37)	NO	22/03/2023	Online	Michela ceola	Social media	Shared project board meeting's photos and brief description of RURALITIES	General public				GMV (P37)
PCS (P1)	NO	29/03/2023	Online	Pedal	Social media	Post on project board meeting	General public				PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	NO	5/04/2023	Online	Pedal	Website	News article on project board meeting	General public				PCS (P1)
PARTICULA GROUP (P8)	NO	28/02/2023	Online	Particula group	Website	News article	General public				PARTICULA GROUP (P8)
PARTICULA GROUP (P8)	NO	28/02/2023	Online	Particula group	Social media	Repost wp6	General public				PARTICULA GROUP (P8)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	24/02/2023	Online	Gheorghită barău, codrin dinu vasiliu	Participation in a workshop	Lag siret-moldova presentation	General public				RDRP (P2)
PARTICULA GROUP (P8)	NO	08/04/2023	Online	Particula group	Social media	Post about project	General public				PARTICULA GROUP (P8)
PARTICULA GROUP (P8)	NO	08/04/2023	Online	Particula group	Social media	Post about project	General public				PARTICULA GROUP (P8)
ACDD (P25)	NO	13/04/2023	Korhogo ,cote d'ivoire	Acdd	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop to present the RURALITIES project and prepare activities with the target groups	General public	50 participants			ACDD (P25)
GMV (P37)	NO	17/04/2023	Online	Giulia busetto	Website	Update of RURALITIES' informations on GMV website	General public				GMV (P37)
ASINCAR (P4)	CTIC (P30), DEX (P35), REDA (P36)	27/02/2023	Online	Roberto morán	Social media	Social media post	General public				ASINCAR (P4)
ASINCAR (P4)		21/03/2023	Online	Roberto morán	Social media	Social media post	General public				ASINCAR (P4)
REDA (P36)	ASINCAR (P4), CTIC (P30), DEX (P35)	07/03/2023	Online	Elena plaza	Website	Post in the reda website about lags webinar	General public				REDA (P36)

REDA (P36)	HITP (P50)	27/03/2023	Inverness, scotland	Paz alvarez	Participation in other type of event	Joint meeting between hitp and rea (taking advantage of the visit of reda to the highlands)	Policy makers	30			REDA (P36)
APRIL 2023 – SEPTEMBER 2023											
INAGRO (P16)	No	27/04/2023	Melle (Belgium)	Reindert Devlamynck	Participation in a Workshop	Circulaire landbouw: vandaag en morgen (ENG: co-creation as a lever for circular innovations.)	Scientific Community	34			INAGRO (P16)
PCS (P1)	No	17/4/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Announcement synergies with project LEAP-RE	General Public	545			PCS (P1)
RRAP (P18)	No	17/04/2023	In person	Špela Sečnik	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop for the development of the Local Development Strategy (Municipality Krško)	General Public	21			RRAP (P18)
RRAP (P18)	No	18/04/2023	In person	Špela Sečnik	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop for the development of the Local Development Strategy (Municipality Krško)	General Public	15			RRAP (P18)
RRAP (P18)	No	19/04/2023	In person	Špela Sečnik	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop for the development of the Local Development Strategy (Municipality Sevnica)	General Public	10			RRAP (P18)
PCS (P1)	No	19/4/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Overview on Africa-EU partnership	General Public	395			PCS (P1)
RRAP (P18)	No	20/04/2023	In person	Špela Sečnik	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop for the development of the Local Development Strategy (Municipality Biustrica ob Sotli)	General Public	6			RRAP (P18)
RRAP (P18)	No	21/04/2023	In person	Špela Sečnik	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop for the development of the Local Development Strategy (Municipality Kostanjevica na Krki)	General Public	11			RRAP (P18)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	21/4/2023	In person (Zlodica, Ceplenița, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Gheorghită Barău	Participation in a Workshop	Rolul ADR Ceplenița la dezvoltarea comunității/ The role of ADR Ceplenița in community development	General Public	18			RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	21/4/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Overview on SIMSES	General Public	571			PCS (P1)

PCS (P1)	No	22/4/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Earth Day	General Public	204			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	23/4/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Overview on participatory governance	General Public	529			PCS (P1)
RRAP (P18)	No	24/04/2023	In person	Špela Sečnik	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop for the development of the Local Development Strategy (Municipality Radeče)	General Public	16			RRAP (P18)
PCS (P1)	No	25/4/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Objective 1: ecosystem-based approach to rural innovation	General Public	167			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	27/4/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Objective 2: characterise six pan-European regions	General Public	586			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	YXSAV (P19), UNIVI (P20). SIRET (P21)	28/04/2023	In person (Iasi University of Life Sciences (IULS), Iași, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Lucian Tanasă, Gheorghită Barău, Diana Creangă, Alexandru Tudoran, Oana Coca	Participation in other type of event	Romanian consortium meeting - Centre rurale de expertiză și formare inteligentă pentru ameliorarea ecosistemelor/ Rural Centers of Expertise and Smart Training for Ecosystem Enhancement	General Public	6			RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	2/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Objective 3: shorten the innovation cycle	General Public	214			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	3/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Objective 4: establish expertise centres	General Public	315			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	5/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Objective 5: establish training centres	General Public	170			PCS (P1)

RDRP (P2)	No	5/05/2023	In person (Ungheni City, Republic of Moldova)	Sebastian Brumă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Lucian Tanasă	Participation in other type of event	Presentation of the RURALITIES project at the cluster meeting in Ungheni City, Republic of Moldova - Round table "Sustainable partnerships between key stakeholders for a quick response to the needs of small farmers and bull breeders in the Ungheni district: Challenges and perspectives", organized by the GREEN FARM Ungheni Cluster	General Public	18			RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	8/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Community-led transdisciplinary knowledge alliance	General Public	160			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	10/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Contributing to improved rural-urban synergies	General Public	185			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	12/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Enabling innovation via citizen science	General Public	149			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	15/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Rethinking business models for just innovation	General Public	160			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	17/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Multi actors quadruple helix approach	General Public	162			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	19/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-1 > Result-driven and lean-agile work plan	General Public	100			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	20/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Today, we celebrate the #worldbeeday	General Public	140			PCS (P1)

PCS (P1)	No	22/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-2 > Shift-driven instrument for tracking and alignment	General Public	152			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	24/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-3 > Measures to ensure an ethical framework	General Public	220			PCS (P1)
RRAP (P18)	No	24/05/2023	In person	Špela Sečnik	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop for the development of the Local Development Strategy	General Public	60			RRAP (P18)
PCS (P1)	No	26/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-4 > Measures to maximise impact and visibility	General Public	96			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	YXSAV (P19)	28/05/2023	In person (Iasi Chamber of Commerce and Industry Iasi, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Lucian Tanasă, Adriana Măgureanu							RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	29/05/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-5 > Engage, connect and empower actors of the rural scene	General Public	237			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	1/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-6 > A framework for ecosystem-enhancing innovation cycle	General Public	209			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	No	4/06/2024	In person (Todirești, Iași county, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă	Social Media	Visit to local producers in the Siret-Moldova LAG territory - Costel Filip, cherry orchard in Todorești, Iași county, Romania	General Public				RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	5/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-7 > Rural expertise to address rural challenges	General Public	120			PCS (P1)

PCS (P1)	No	12/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-8 > Learning framework to accelerate rural innovation	General Public	105			PCS (P1)
GMV (P37)	No	14/06/2023	Online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Introduction of RURALITIES on instagram	General Public				GMV (P37)
PCS (P1)	No	14/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	WP-4 > Ensuring a holistic impact dimension for real-scale change	General Public	122			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	16/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	EU Agenda > Delivering on the '2023 European Year of Skills'	General Public	23			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	19/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Synergies > Delivering on sustainable food systems	General Public	37			PCS (P1)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37)	20/06/2023	Online	Viola Gaudiano, Giulia Busetto, Irene Gasparella	Organisation of a conference	Presentation of the RURALITIES project at the conference of mayors of the "Altopiano dei 7 comuni" and involvement of the same in mapping the stakeholders	Regional/Local authorities	9			FHV (P31)
PCS (P1)	No	21/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Coordination and support mechanisms	General Public	138			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	23/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	A transdisciplinary coordination and support action	General Public	133			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	26/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	A transdisciplinary coordination and support action	General Public	521			PCS (P1)
GMV (P37)	No	28/06/2023	Online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Explanation of the problems that will be faced	General Public				GMV (P37)
PCS (P1)	No	28/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	The intervention area (SIMSES) in the region of Asturias (Spain)	General Public	483			PCS (P1)

PCS (P1)	No	30/06/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	The intervention area (SIMSES) in the region of Siret-Moldova (Romania)	General Public	177			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	No	01-02/07/2023	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Sonia Bulei, Lucian Tanasă	Trade fair	Cherry Festival - Promotion of local producers from the Siret-Moldova LAG territory among consumers in the city of Iasi	General Public				RDRP (P2)
GMV (P37)	No	13/07/2023	Online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Project solutions	General Public				GMV (P37)
PCS (P1)	No	3/07/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	The intervention area (SIMSES) in the region of Veneto (Italy)	General Public	318			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	26/07/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	The intervention area (SIMSES) in Scotland, UK	General Public	313			PCS (P1)
GMV (P37)	No	27/07/2023	Online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Project's approach	General Public				GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)	No	03/08/2023	Online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Project's approach	General Public				GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)	No	30/08/2023	Online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	project implementation area	General Public				GMV (P37)
PCS (P1)	IRI (P7)	20/09/2023	Online	Gabor Mester	Participation in a Workshop	Workshop FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network	Scientific Community	175			PCS (P1)
IRI (P1)	PCS (P1)	20/09/2023	Online	Sinisa Borota	Participation in a Workshop	Workshop FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network	National authorities and associations	175			IRI (P1)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	04/09/2023	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă	Social Media	Identification of local producers who deliver products to the Iași market within the RURALITIES project - Farmer Costel Filip from Todirești, Iași county	General Public				RDRP (P2)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37)	30/10/2023			Press release	Dalle vie dei pellegrini un nuovo impulso al turismo	General Public				FHV (P31)
OCTOBER 2023 – MARCH 2024											
PCS (P1)	No	2/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	The intervention area (SIMSES) in the Posavje Region, Slovenia	General Public	713			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	4/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Events Partners' meeting in Inverness, UK	General Public	538			PCS (P1)

RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	07/10/2023	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă	Social Media	Promoting a trade fair: "The village in dishes" - Revival of the Dacia agri-food market ("Satul în bucate" - Piața Dacia)	General Public				RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)	No	07-08/10/2023	In person (Dacia agri-food market, Iasi, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Lucian Tanasă, Sonia Bulei	Trade fair	"The village in dishes" - Revival of the Dacia agri-food market ("Satul în bucate" - Piața Dacia)	General Public				RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	9/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Support The intervention area (SIMSES) in the Marche Region, Italy	General Public	379			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	12/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Innovation Enabling progress beyond the state-of-the-art	General Public	418			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	16/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Innovation Maximising impact beyond the regional panorama	General Public	452			PCS (P1)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37)	18/10/2023	Asiago	Viola Gaudiano Giulia Busetto Irene Gasparella	Organisation of a conference	presentation of the project to the socio-economic representatives of the plateau area	Policy makers	8			FHV (P31)
PCS (P1)	No	16/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Innovation Exploring citizen science to enable insightful monitoring	General Public	440			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	20/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Innovation Structuring synergistic mechanisms and foster collaborative innovation	General Public	574			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	23/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Innovation Simplified Rural Socio-Ecological Systems (SIMSES)	General Public	504			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	24/10/2023	In person (Ceplenița, Iasi County, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Lucian Tanasă, Sonia Bulei	Participation in other type of event	RURALITIES Project presentation & Identification of stakeholders in the territory of Siret Moldova LAG	General Public	48			RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	25/10/2023	In person (Todirești, Hărmănești & Cotnari, Iasi County, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Lucian Tanasă, Sonia Bulei	Participation in other type of event	RURALITIES Project presentation & Identification of stakeholders in the territory of Siret Moldova LAG	General Public	64			RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	26/10/2023	In person (Valea Seacă, Lespezi & Vânători, Iasi County, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Lucian Tanasă, Sonia Bulei	Participation in other type of event	RURALITIES Project presentation & Identification of stakeholders in the territory of Siret Moldova LAG	General Public	42			RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	25/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Prevalence Digitally-enhanced multi actors approach	General Public	284			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	27/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Enablers Establishing expert centres in rural innovation	General Public	314			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	30/10/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Assessment Developing a comprehensive situation analysis of challenges	General Public	566			PCS (P1)

PCS (P1)	No	1/11/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Health A multifaceted approach to healthcare innovation	General Public	359			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	6/11/2023	In person (Ceplenița & Cotnari, Iași County, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Gheorghe Barău, Lucian Tanasă	Participation in a Workshop	Environmentally friendly farming systems - Assessments, opportunities, challenges, needs	General Public				RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	6/11/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	November 6th, 2023 Digital Empowering rural communities to thrive in the digital age	General Public	456			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	7/11/2023	In person (Ceplenița & Cotnari, Iași County, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Gheorghe Barău, Lucian Tanasă	Participation in a Workshop	Environmentally friendly farming systems - Assessments, opportunities, challenges, needs	General Public				RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	8/11/2023	In person (Ceplenița & Cotnari, Iași County, Romania)	Sebastian Brumă, Gheorghe Barău, Lucian Tanasă	Participation in a Workshop	Environmentally friendly farming systems - Assessments, opportunities, challenges, needs	General Public				RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	10/11/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	November 10th, 2023 Mobility Climate smart and inclusive mobility solutions for rural areas	General Public	230			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	No	16/11/2023	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă	Participation in a Conference	Participatory governance in the community of beneficiaries from LAG Siret Moldova – Knowledge and action for rural development in the RURALITIES project/ Guvernanta participativa in comunitatea beneficiarilor din GAL Siret Moldova – Cunoastere si actiune pentru dezvoltare rurala in proiectul RURALITIES (2023 SAAR National Symposium)	General Public	46			RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)	SIRET (P21)	19/11/2023	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Gheorghe Barău	Social Media	Participation in the TV show "Time of return" (on Trinitas TV) and the promotion of the RURALITIES project (Mihaela Popescu, Costel Filip, Ioan Sebastian Brumă)	General Public				RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	23/11/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	November 21st, 2023 Events Showcasing the project RURALITIES climate-smart innovation action	General Public	241			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	No	4/12/2023	Online	Codrin Dinu Vasiliu Ioan Sebastian Brumă	Participation in a Workshop	RoRuralia, Living Lab Presentation - Romanian Living & Policy Lab in RURALITIES Project	General Public				RDRP (P2)

				Lucian Tanasă Sonia Bulei							
PCS (P1)	No	6/12/2023	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	December 6th, 2023 Promotion Contribution to the project visibility	General Public	260			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	22/12/2023	Online	Gabor MESTER	Social Media	The RURALITIES team sends warm wishes for a fantastic and peaceful Winter Break!	General Public	287			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	8/01/2024	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	January 8th, 2024 Change Climate smart and inclusive solutions for rural areas in 2024	General Public	254			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	10/01/2024	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	January 10th, 2024 Progress Supporting agroecosystems towards accurate policy-making	General Public	229			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	12/01/2024	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	January 12th, 2024 Climate action Supporting mitigation and adaptation to climate change	General Public	192			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	15/01/2024	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	January 15th, 2024 Innovation action Unique challenges and opportunities for rural communities	General Public	164			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	No	17/01/2024	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	January 17th, 2024 Impact 1.000+ facilitators to trigger, foster and sustain rural innovation	General Public	152			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	YXSAV (P19), UNIVI (P20), SIRET (P1)	18/01/2024	Online	Authors: Ioan Sebastian Brumă and Lucian Tanasă Facilitators: Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Sonia Bulei, Diana Creangă, Adriana Măgureanu, Alexandru Tudoran, Raluca Rusu,	Organisation of a workshop	Capacity Building - Knowledge Management Workshop (KTL-CBW)	General Public	8			RDRP (P2)
PCS (P1)	No	19/01/2024	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	January 19th, 2024 Events RURALITIES engages in a panoply of purposeful events by the EU	General Public	137			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	No	24/01/2024	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Lucian	Organisation of a workshop	Small producers' access to local markets/	General Public				RDRP (P2)

				Tanasă, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu		Accesul micilor producători agroalimentari la piețele locale (RoRuralia training workshop)					
PCS (P1)	No	26/01/2024	Online	Bruno SALES da SILVA	Social Media	Synergies Introducing rurAllure, a sister project of RURALITIES	General Public	503			PCS (P1)
RDRP (P2)	No	30/01/2024	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă (All authors: Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Mihai Alexandru Chițea, Alexandra Raluca Jelea1, Lorena Florentina Chițea, Roxana Nicoleta Rațu, Mihaela Popa)	Press release	The Evolution of the Romanian Organic Agriculture in a Global Context (Scientific Article)	Scientific Community				RDRP (P2)
ASINCAR (P4)		15/11/2023	online	Roberto Morán	Social Media	Social media post	General Public				ASINCAR (P4)
ASINCAR (P4)	CTIC (P30)	15/11/2023	online	Roberto Morán	Social Media	Social media post	General Public				ASINCAR (P4)
ASINCAR (P4)	CTIC (P30)	16/11/2023	f2f	Roberto Morán	Participation in a Workshop	Informative workshop about Horizon Europe (Jornada informativa Horizonte Europa)	Industry	40			ASINCAR (P4)
IRI (P7)		6/12/2023	Online	Sinisa Borota and Marina Andjelkovic	Social Media	Social media post	General Public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		6/12/2023	Online	Sinisa Borota and Marina Andjelkovic	Social Media	Social media post	General Public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		6/12/2023	Online	Sinisa Borota and Marina Andjelkovic	Social Media	Social media post	General Public				IRI (P7)
CTIC (P30)		5/12/2023	Online	Covadonga Cima		"LinkedIn post to promote visibility for the first workshop presenting the existing living labs in the project."	General Public				CTIC (P30)
RDRP (P2)		13/02/2024	Online	Ioan Brumă Sebastian, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu	Trade fair	Social media post - participation of our RURALITIES stakeholder, Magazia Moraritei - Paine cu maia coapta pe vatra, at Biofach 2024 - Nürnberg, Germany	General Public				RDRP (P2)

RDRP (P2)		29/02/2024	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă	Press release	Contributor at FAO - Family Farming Knowledge Platform with the article "The Evolution of the Romanian Organic Agriculture in a Global Context" (journal article in RURALITIES project)	General Public				RDRP (P2)
IRI (P7)		12/03/2024	In person	Sinisa Borota	Participation in other type of event	Introduction to the Regenerative Agriculture Alliance of Serbia	General Public	130			IRI (P7)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37)	20/03/2024	in person	Viola Gaudiano and Giulia Busetto	Organisation of a workshop	"The slow, cultural, and sustainable tourism in the Asiago Plateau. Sharing, co-designing, and innovating."	Civil Society	15			FHV (P31)
RDRP (P2)		22/03/2024	Online	Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Ioan Sebastian Brumă	Press release	Newsletter no. 2/2024 in RRN Romania (National Rural Network) "CENTRUL DE EXCELENȚĂ CESAR2030 ÎN SOCIO-ECONOMIA ALIMENTARĂ" (CESAR2030 CENTER OF EXCELLENCE IN FOOD SOCIO-ECONOMY)	General Public				RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)		27/03/2024	Online	Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Sonia Bulei, Lucian Tanasă	Website	RoRuralia Living Lab website https://roruralia.rdrp.org	General Public				RDRP (P2)
RDRP (P2)		28/03/2024	Online	Ioan Sebastian Brumă	Social Media	Work visit in Probotă, Iași County, Romania - Probotă Mill and Morărița Grocery (Moara Probotă & Magazia Morăriței)	General Public	15			RDRP (P2)
CTIC (P30)	ASIN(P4) DEX(P35) REDA (P36)	2/02/2024	Online	Covadonga Cima	Social Media	LinkedIn post to discuss the in-person meeting of the Asturias Hub to talk about the project's status and the next steps to take	General Public				CTIC (P30)
CTIC (P30)	NO	29/02/2024	Online	Covadonga Cima	Social Media	LinkedIn post to raise awareness about the workshop held with other project partners where our CTIC Rural Tech living lab was presented.	General Public				CTIC (P30)
MARIN (P14)	NO	19–20/02/2024	Kenya		Participation in other type of event	Participation in the 7th Africa Agri Expo (AAE) 2024 held on February 19th and 20th in Kenya	General Public				MARIN (P14)
PCS (P1)	NO	15/02/2024	Online		Social Media	Rural Revival webinar invitation	General Public	68			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	NO	21/02/2024	Online		Social Media	Launch of RURALITIES Training Material	General Public	393			PCS (P1)

PCS (P1)	NO	23/02/2024	Online		Social Media	New Initiative in Mauritania: Environmental Education	General Public	317			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	NO	29/02/2024	Online		Social Media	Leap Day 2024 Not the every*day* at RURALITIES, a leap of rural wisdom	General Public	328			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	NO	8/03/2024	Online		Social Media	Celebrating Concerted effort towards gender equity within RURALITIES	General Public	405			PCS (P1)
APRIL 2024 – SEPTEMBER 2024											
FHV (P31)		5/04/2024	in person	Viola Gaudiano	Pitch event	Project pitch with Prof. Orio, Head of Cultural tourism planning and management and Tourism, Cultural Heritage, Sustainability Course at University of Padua	Scientific Community	3			FHV (P31)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37)	16/04/2024	in person	Viola Gaudiano and Giulia Busetto	Pitch event	Project pitch with Prof. Scipioni, Founder and CEO of Spin Life	Industry	3			FHV (P31)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37)	16/04/2024	in person	Viola Gaudiano and Giulia Busetto	Pitch event	Project pitch with the Headmaster and 4 teachers from Rigoni Stern High School in Asiago	Scientific Community	5			FHV (P31)
CTIC (P30)	NO	29/02/2024	Online	Covadonga Cima	Social Media	Sharing on LinkedIn to raise awareness about the leaflet created by CETRI to promote the project	General Public				CTIC (P30)
PCS (P1)	NO	03/07/2024	Tunisia	Gabor Mester	Participation in other type of event	EU Funding Opportunities under Horizon Europe: Focus on Widening Calls	Scientific Community	180			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	NO	04/07/2024	Online	Gabor Mester	Social Media	Linked in post about EU Funding Opportunities under Horizon Europe: Focus on Widening Calls	Civil Society	380			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	NO	04/07/2024	Online	Gabor Mester	Social Media	LinkedIn post on PEDAL's profile about EU Funding Opportunities under Horizon Europe: Focus on Widening Calls	Civil Society	2000			PCS (P1)
PCS (P1)	NO	05/07/2024	Online	Gabor Mester	Website	Website article on PEDAL's website about EU Funding Opportunities under Horizon Europe: Focus on Widening Calls	Civil Society	Will check at the end of RP			PCS (P1)
IRI (P7)	NO	25/06/2024	Novi Sad, Serbia	Sinisa Borota	Participation in other type of event	BEAMING Summer School on Open Science	Scientific Community	40			IRI (P7)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	22/03/2024	Online	Giulia Busetto, Viola Gaudiano	Other	"Thank you for sharing your experience". Engagement and thank-you email for the facilitators who participated in the meeting on March 20 .	Civil Society	20			GMV (P37)

GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	3/07/2024	Online	Giulia Busetto, Viola Gaudiano	Other	Monthly communication to facilitators "Welcome back to RURALITIES"	Civil Society	30			GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	15/07/2024	Online	Giulia Busetto, Viola Gaudiano	Other	"Ready to innovate the Seven Municipalities Plateau!"	Civil Society	57			GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	20/03/2024	Online	Giulia Busetto, Viola Gaudiano	Other	Recall:"Ready to innovate the Seven Municipalities Plateau!"	Civil Society	57			GMV (P37)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37) IISAC (P49)	23-24/09/2024	Asiago, Italy	Viola Gaudiano	Other	Two days of brainstorming between Fondazione Homo Viator and Istituto Cecchi to share best practices. Also met with partner GAL Montagna Vicentina, visited the Istituto Rigoni Stern in Asiago, and the Bisele farm, which combines a biological approach with the education of younger generations		5			FHV (P31)
OCTOBER 2024 – MARCH 2025											
REDA (P36)	No	15/10/2024	Candás, Asturias	Paz Álvarez Rosal	Organisation of a conference	Rural women day	General Public	150			REDA (P36)
ASINCAR (P4)	No	31/10/2024	Asturias	Cristina Viera	Press release	Asincarc inicia la difusión del proyecto europeo RURALITIES -EN 'Asincarc starts promotion of RURALITIES european project'	General Public	198000			ASINCAR (P4)
ASINCAR (P4)	No	15/11/2024	Asturias	Cristina Viera	Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	Onda cero - Más de uno program	General Public				ASINCAR (P4)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	7/11/2024	Online	Giulia Busetto, Viola Gaudiano	Other	Monthly communication to facilitators "RURALITIES: New Opportunities to Innovate the Plateau!"	Civil Society	57			GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)		31/10/2024	Online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Facebook and Instagram post on General Assembly in Zagreb	General Public				GMV (37)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	13/11/2024	Online	Giulia Busetto	Website	Updated the page dedicated to RURALITIES with meetings and workshops held	General Public				GMV (37)
PCS (P1)		15.11.2024	Online	Gabor Mester	Website	RURALITIES as sister project on ENTRACK's project website	General Public				PEDAL (1)

INAG (P16)	No	13/03/2025	In person (West Flanders)	Nele Dejonckheere	Participation in a Workshop	Networkevent West-Flemish visiting farms 'Krokusreceptie'	General Public	50			Inag (16)
NIC (P5)	No	8/02/2025	Ljubljana (Slovenia)	Mirica Karlovits, Uroš Novak	Organisation of a workshop	Molekularni cukrčki (Molecular candies)	General Public	150			NIC
ASIN (P4)	CTIC, REDA (P36), DEX (P35)	20/02/2025	Online (Spain)	Cristina Viera, Cecilia Penín, Covadonga Cima, Juan Lázaro y Paz Álvarez Rosal	Other	Internal meeting for follow-up and defining upcoming events/activities		5			ASINCAR
ASIN (P4)	No	21/02/2025	Noreña (Spain)	Cristina Viera	Other	Internal meeting for follow-up and defining upcoming events/activities. Brainstorming within ASINCAR		30			ASINCAR
HITP (P50)	No	28/02/2025	Scotland, UK	Katy Beasley	Social Media	Rural Thrive campaign post 1	General Public				HITRANS
HITP (P50)	No	3/03/2025	Scotland, UK	Katy Beasley	Social Media	Rural Thrive campaign post 2	General Public				HITRANS
GMV (P37)		28/02/2025	online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Rural thrive campaign post 1	General Public				GMV (37)
RRAP (P18)	No	26/02/2025	Krško, Slovenia	Ana Jurečič Martinčič	Organisation of a workshop	Housing Provision in Posavje Region	Regional/Local authorities	17	Yes (name, e-mail, organization)	Communicating the results of the workshop	RRAP (18)
EVRO (P47)	RRAP (P18), SEVO (P48)	7/03/2025	Krško, Slovenia	Marolt Andreja, Anton Petrovič	Organisation of a workshop	Topaz Apple and Local Traditions Day	General Public	90			EVRO (47)
RRAP (P18)		12/03/2025	Krško, Slovenia	Ana Jurečič Martinčič	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop - Design of the Masterplan for Sustainable Tourism Development in the Sava River Basin					RRAP (18)
INAG (P16)	No	05/03/2025	Roeselare, Belgium	Reindert Devlamynck	Exhibition	Field visit within workshop organised by ENOLL called <i>Tools and Resources for Accelerating Soil Living Lab Development</i>	Scientific Community	16			Inag (16)

GMV (P37)		07/03/2025	online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Rural thrive campaign post 2 - Launch event of LL SmartAltopiano	General Public				GMV (37)
GMV (P37)		07/03/2025	online		Press release	SmartAltopiano: un progetto dedicato al turismo lento, culturale e sostenibile					GMV (37)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	17/02/2025	online	Giulia Busetto	Organisation of a workshop	Invitation to the launch event of the Living Lab SmartAltopiano at Bisele Farm	Regional/Local authorities	100			GMV (37)
GMV (P37)		07/03/2025	online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Sharing of the event in the GAL newsletter	General Public	1256			GMV (37)
GMV (P37)		21/03/2025	online	Giulia Busetto	Social Media	Rural thrive campaign post 3 - Quote of LAG Director Irene Gasparella	General Public				GMV (37)
GMV (P37) FHV (P31)		26/03/2025	Italy	Viola Gaudiano Giulia Busetto Irene Gasparella	Organisation of a workshop	Event launch of the Living Lab SmartAltopiano	Civil Society	25-30			GMV (37) FHV (31)
APRIL 2025 – SEPTEMBER 2025											
GMV (P37)		02/04/2025	online		Social Media	Facebook&Ig post about the event	General Public	1143 views, 18 likes 4 share			GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)		04/04/2025	online		Website	News on LAG website about the event launch	General Public				GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)		08/04/2025	online		Website	Living Lab SmartAltopiano section on LAG website	General Public				GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)		09/04/2025	online		Organisation of a workshop	April NL with Webinar gamification in tourism invitation	General Public	audience 111			GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)		14/04/2025	online		Social Media	Facebook&Ig post about the webinar	General Public	291 views, 7 likes			GMV (P37)
FHV (P31)	GMV (P37)	17/04/2025	online		Organisation of a workshop	Webinar Gamification in tourism	General Public	13 people	Residence - Name/last name	To identify how many people from the Asiago Plateau subscribed	FHV (P31)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	28/04/2025	online		Social Media	Webinar Follow up NL	General Public	audience 129			GMV (P37)

RRAP (P18)	EVRO (P47)	21/05/2025	public event		Participation in other type of event	Learning Parade 2025	General Public		yes, name/surname and organization	To collect data for possible cooperation	RRAP (P18)
FHV (P31)			online		Participation in a Workshop	Good Practice Webinar on rural innovation	General Public				FHV (P31)
PCS (P1)	PCS (P1)	12/06/2025	Brussels, Belgium		Participation in a Conference	EUSEW 2025	Policy makers	1000+	no		PCS (P1)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	07/05/2025	online		Social Media	May Newsletter- Tourism, Innovation, and Opportunities for Territories: The Best of May with RURALITIES	General Public	audience 129			GMV (P37)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	17/06/2025	online		Social Media	June Newsletter- RURALITIES June among local networks, good practices, and rural innovation	General Public	audience 117			GMV (P37)
FHV (P31)		23/06/2025	Schio (Veneto, Italy)		Organisation of a workshop		Regional/Local authorities	20	Yes, emails	Follow up and further involvements /FHV database	FHV (P31)
FHV (P31)	APO	30/06/2025	online		Training/Seminar	Africa Initiative III	National authorities and associations	1269 views	No		FHV (P31)
IRI (P7)		23/04/2025	online		Social Media	Conducted activities on the Programme 3 of the IRI	General Public	1129 impressions, 23 reactions			IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		23/04/2025	online		Social Media	Conducted activities on the Programme 3 of the IRI	General Public	97 views, 6 reactions			IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		23/04/2025	online		Social Media	Conducted activities on the Programme 3 of the IRI	General Public	528 reach, 11 reactions			IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		23/04/2025	online		Social Media	Conducted activities on the Programme 3 of the IRI	General Public	20 views, 2 reactions			IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		29/04/2025	online		Website	Consortium meeting in Denmark	General Public				IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		29/04/2025	online		Social Media	Consortium meeting in Denmark	General Public	570 impressions, 17 reactions			IRI (P7)

IRI (P7)		29/04/2025	online		Social Media	Consortium meeting in Denmark	General Public	124 views, 4 reactions			IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		29/04/2025	online		Social Media	Consortium meeting in Denmark	General Public	572 reach, 17 reactions			IRI (P7)
IRI (P7)		29/04/2025	online		Social Media	Consortium meeting in Denmark	General Public	16 views, 1 reaction			IRI (P7)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	18/07/2025	online		Social Media	July Newsletter- RURALITIES July among trails, participation, and visions for rural tourism	General Public	audience 116			GMV (P37)
PCS (P1)		24/07/2025	online		Social Media	The ESIRA Project and Project RURALITIES are joining forces as sister projects - social media posts on ESIRA's channels (LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram)	General Public				PCS (P1)
GMV (P37)	FHV (P31)	11/09/2025	online		Social Media	RURALITIES Settembre tra dati, nuove professioni e turismo montano	General Public	audience 114			GMV (P37)
ASINCAR (P4)		25/08/2025	In person		Flyer/Leaflet/poster	RURALITIES leaflet were offered in FIDMA -international fair hold in Gijón Asturias. ASINCAR participated in the fair promoting their local brand 'Alimentos del Paraiso'	General Public	visitors to the fair >700.000 (according to organizers data)			ASINCAR (P4)
PCS (P1)		6/09/2025	In person	N/A	Exhibition	AGROKOMPLEX, Slovakia	Industry	92000 visitors			PCS (P1)

Table 4 – Data collection log

5. CONCLUSIONS

This update of the RURALITIES project's Data Management Plan (DMP) represents a significant milestone in the consolidation of a robust, ethical, and sustainable strategy for data management in the field of rural innovation. Throughout this version, substantial improvements have been incorporated that reflect the accumulated learning, regulatory developments, and practical experience acquired by the consortium partners.

One of the most significant advances has been the **progress in the utilization of the Zenodo repository**, which centralizes the publication of experimental data generated by the various partners. This repository guarantees data accessibility and traceability and promotes reuse through open licenses (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International), aligning with the FAIR principles. The publication of high-quality datasets, such as studies on organic agriculture, sustainable fertilization, and rural anthropology, demonstrates the project's commitment to scientific transparency and knowledge transfer.

In parallel, the **development and implementation of the 2ES monitoring framework** have enabled the establishment of an effective system for gathering evidence on the impact of project activities. With more than 130 registered activities so far, the 2ES framework has facilitated the assessment of economic, social, and environmental impacts, integrating key indicators such as the participation of youth, women, vulnerable groups, rural experts, and political actors. This multidimensional approach has been essential to validate the effectiveness of project actions in SIMSES territories.

From a legal and ethical perspective, the DMP has thoroughly addressed two critical aspects: the **management of personal data in the multi-stakeholder repository** and **obtaining informed consent from illiterate people**. In the former, a detailed analysis of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) was conducted, concluding that, under certain exceptions (such as public interest and scientific research), the project can continue collecting public data without the need to contact each stakeholder individually. In the second case, specific protocols have been established to ensure informed consent, even in low-literacy settings, using impartial witnesses, oral presentations, and audiovisual documentation. These measures are integrated into **D3.3 – Report on the Framework for Human Participation, Animal Ethics, Environment, Health, and Safety (M36)**. The Ethics Manager (UNIZG) and the coordinator (PEDAL) are responsible for ensuring adherence to these protocols in all future activities.

Furthermore, **effective implementation of data management policies** has been demonstrated in project activities. Although most dissemination activities do not involve the collection of personal data, specific cases have been identified where sensitive data (such as names, email addresses, or place of residence) are handled. In these cases, appropriate protection measures have been implemented, and a responsible partner has been designated to ensure regulatory compliance.

RURALITIES has established a cybersecurity framework that aligns with both the **GDPR** and the **NIS2 Directive**, ensuring that personal data is managed securely, transparently, and ethically. By combining technical safeguards (MFA, secure cloud environments) with procedural measures (audits, breach notification protocols, privacy by design), the consortium provides strong protection for all participants and reinforces compliance with EU ethical and legal standards throughout the project lifecycle.

Overall, the updated DMP meets the requirements of the Horizon Europe program and establishes a replicable framework for other rural innovation projects. The combination of digital tools, participatory methodologies, an ethical approach, and a commitment to sustainability positions RURALITIES as a European benchmark in data management in rural settings.

Finally, this deliverable reaffirms that data management is a strategic dimension that directly influences the quality, impact, and legitimacy of project outcomes. The evolution of the DMP reflects the consortium's ability to adapt to new challenges, integrate best practices, and ensure that the data generated contribute significantly to smart, inclusive, and resilient rural development.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is conceived as a **living document**, subject to continuous updates throughout the second phase of the project and will be updated at the end of the project as **D1.5 – Data Management Plan (Final Version at M60)**.